

Calculation of the Raman frequencies as a function of temperature in phase I of benzene

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Abstract : This study gives our calculation of the Raman frequencies of the lattice modes $A (A_{1g})$, $B (A_g B_{2g})$ and $C (B_{1g} B_{3g})$ as a function of temperature at constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa for the solid phase I of benzene. The Raman frequencies of those lattice modes are calculated using the volume data from the literature through the mode Grüneisen parameters for the solid phase I of this molecular crystal. It is shown here that the Raman frequencies of the lattice modes studied decrease with increasing temperature, as expected and they also decrease as the pressure increases in the solid phase I of benzene.

Keywords : Raman frequency, Grüneisen parameter, solid phase I, benzene.

Introduction

Benzene exhibits various solid phases, liquid, decomposed compounds and polymer phases, as given in the P-T phase diagrams¹⁻⁷. Solid phase I is transformed into the solid phase II at 270 °C and as the pressure is increased further, solid benzene III occurs². Among the phases of liquid, solid I and solid II, a triple point was observed² and, a second triple point was also obtained at the temperature of 590 ± 15 °C and the pressure of 40 kbar³, as given in the T-P phase diagram⁵. Using the experimental phase diagram⁵, we have constructed the phase line equations for all the phases of benzene by the mean field theory^{7,8}. Thermodynamic properties of crystalline benzene have been investigated using various experimental techniques as reported in the literature. Pressure-volume-temperature relations for reorientational crystalline benzene have been obtained experimentally from -20 to 51 °C for pressures to 5 kbar⁹. Isothermal variation of molar volume of benzene has been determined experimentally at various pressures¹⁰. Molar volume has been measured as a function of temperature^{11,12} and pressure and the Grüneisen parameters have been inferred in the different phases of benzene¹². The thermal expansivity

has been measured at various pressures along isotherms in solid benzene and at melting¹³. Using the experimental data for the molar volume near the melting lines^{9,13}, we have analyzed the molar volume as a function of temperature¹⁴ and pressure¹⁵ in our earlier studies.

The spectroscopic studies on the solid and liquid phases of benzene have also been reported in the literature. Far infrared spectroscopy¹⁶, X-ray¹⁷, infrared¹⁸ and Raman spectroscopy studies^{5,6,12,19-21} have been given previously. Using the volume data¹² and the Raman frequency data⁶, we have calculated the Raman frequencies at various pressures through the mode Grüneisen parameter in phase II of solid benzene in our recent study²². In this study, we calculate the Raman frequencies at various temperatures in phase I of benzene.

Calculations and results

Temperature (or pressure) dependence of the volume V and frequency ν can be correlated by the mode Grüneisen parameter defined as

$$\gamma = \frac{d \ln V}{d \ln \nu} \quad (1)$$

If one takes the temperature dependence of V and ν at

constant pressure, the isobaric mode Grüneisen parameter γ_P can be defined as

$$\gamma_P = - \frac{V}{\nu} (\partial \nu / \partial T)_P / (\partial V / \partial T)_P \quad (2)$$

From this definition, the temperature dependence of the frequency can be obtained as follows :

$$\nu_P(T) = A(P) + \nu_1 \exp [-\gamma_P \ln (V_P(T)/V_1)] \quad (3)$$

where the pressure-dependent term can be expressed as

$$A(P) = a_0 + a_1 P + a_2 P^2 \quad (4)$$

with the constants a_0 , a_1 and a_2 . In eq. (3) ν_1 and V_1 are the extrapolated values of the frequency and volume at a constant temperature at zero pressure ($P = 0$), respectively. We calculated here the Raman frequencies of the three lattice modes, namely, the A (A_{1g}), B ($A_g B_{2g}$) and C ($B_{1g} B_{3g}$) as a function of temperature for constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa in the solid phase I of benzene using the volume data¹² according to eq. (3). For this calculation, we first analyzed the temperature dependence of the observed volume at zero pressure ($P = 0$ GPa) for the solid phase I of benzene according to the quadratic relation,

$$V = a + bT + cT^2 \quad (5)$$

where a , b and c are constants. Values of those coefficients from our analysis are given in Table 1. The extrapolated values of the volume at various temperatures and pressures (eq. (5)) are given in Table 2. We also needed to analyze the pressure dependence of some observed¹² values of the Raman frequencies for the lattice modes (A , B and C), which were used as the initial data according to the relation,

$$\nu = b_0 + b_1 P + b_2 P^2 \quad (6)$$

Table 1. Values of the coefficients according to eq. (4) for the phase I of benzene

a (cm ³)	b (cm ³ /K)	c (cm ³ /K ²)
69.38	$=1.47 \times 10^{-2}$	1.42×10^{-4}

Table 2. Extrapolated values of the volume data¹² at various temperatures and pressures for the phase I of benzene (eq. (5))

T (K)	V (cm ³)	P (GPa)	V (cm ³)
274	76	0	77.3
294	77.3	1.4	66.0
300	77.7	3.05	61.8

where b_0 , b_1 and b_2 are constants. From our analysis, we obtained the values of those coefficients, as given in Table 3. This then gave us the values of the Raman frequencies (eq. (6)) of the lattice modes (A , B and C) for constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa, which we give in Table 4. Those values of the Raman frequencies for the three lattice modes (Table 4) were used to determine the pressure-dependent term $A(P)$ with the coefficients

Table 3. Values of the coefficients according to eq. (5) for the Raman bands indicated. Values of the mode Grüneisen parameter (γ_T , γ_P) and the values of the Raman frequency ν_1 at $P = 0$ ($T = 294$ K) for the lattice modes are also given here for the phase I of benzene

Raman bands	b_0 (cm ⁻¹)	b_1 (cm ⁻¹ /GPa)	b_2 (cm ⁻¹ /GPa ²)	γ_T	ν_1 (cm ⁻¹)
A (A_{1g})	44.94	20.54	-2.48	3.0	44.94
B ($A_g B_{2g}$)	64.35	27.19	-3.50	2.5	64.35
C ($B_{1g} B_{3g}$)	105.45	49.49	-6.33	3.0	105.45

Table 4. Values of the Raman frequencies of the lattice modes indicated for three pressures according to eq. (6) for the phase I of benzene

P (GPa)	ν_P (cm ⁻¹)		
	Mode A	Mode B	Mode C
0	44.94	64.35	105.45
1.4	68.84	95.56	162.33
3.05	84.52	114.72	197.51

a_0 , a_1 and a_2 (eq. (4)) using the volume values (Table 2) and the experimental¹² values of mode Grüneisen parameter γ_T for the solid phase I of benzene through eq. (3). We assumed here the experimental γ_T ($T = 294$ K) values to be the same as the γ_P ($P = 0$) in eq. (3), as given in Table 3. In eq. (3), V_1 was taken as the extrapolated value of volume (eq. (5)) at $T = 300$ K and $P = 0$ GPa (Table 2) and, the values of ν_1 for the lattice modes of A , B and C were extracted from eq. (6) at $T = 294$ K and $P = 0$ GPa. Using the observed volume data¹², values of the Raman frequencies for the lattice modes (A , B and C) (Table 4) at various temperatures for constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa with the values of γ_P , ν_1 (Table 3) and V_1 (Table 2), the coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 were determined for the solid phase I of benzene, as given in Table 5. Once the coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 were determined, we were then able to calculate the temperature dependence of the Raman frequencies of the lattice modes (A , B and C) for constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05

Table 5. Values of the coefficients for the lattice modes indicated according to eq. (4) for the phase I of benzene

Raman bands	a_0 (cm ⁻¹)	a_1 (cm ⁻¹ /GPa)	a_2 (cm ⁻¹ /GPa ²)
A (A_{1g})	-0.70	3.87	0.83
B ($A_g B_{2g}$)	-0.84	0.92	0.46
C ($B_{1g} B_{3g}$)	1.65	11.21	2.20

GPa according to eq. (3). We plot the temperature dependence of mode *A* for constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa for phase I of benzene in Fig. 1. Similarly, Figs. 2 and 3 give our plots for the lattice modes *B* and *C*, respectively for phase I of benzene.

Fig. 1. The Raman frequency calculated as a function of temperature for the lattice mode *A* (A_{1g}) for constant pressures indicated for the phase I of benzene according to eq. (3).

Fig. 2. The Raman frequency calculated as a function of temperature for the lattice mode *B* ($A_g B_{2g}$) for constant pressures indicated for the phase I of benzene according to eq. (3).

Fig. 3. The Raman frequency calculated as a function of temperature for the lattice mode *C* ($B_{1g} B_{3g}$) for constant pressures indicated for the phase I of benzene according to eq. (3).

Discussion

As shown in Figs. (1-3), the Raman frequencies of the lattice modes *A*, *B* and *C* decrease with increasing temperature in the solid phase I of benzene at constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa. This is the expected behaviour of the lattice modes whose Raman frequencies should also decrease as constant pressures increase (Figs. 1-3). However, the Raman frequencies of the lattice mode *B* do not show this expected behaviour, where the Raman frequencies for $P = 3.05$ GPa are higher than those for $P = 0$ and 1.4 GPa (Fig. 2). In fact, the Raman frequencies of this lattice mode (*B*) are almost the same for constant pressures of 0 and 1.4 GPa (Fig. 2). For the lattice mode *A*, the Raman frequencies are nearly the same for the pressures of 1.4 and 3.05 GPa (Fig. 1), whereas for the lattice mode *C* the Raman frequencies at those pressures (1.4 and 3.05 GPa) are very close to each other (Fig. 3).

The Raman frequencies of the lattice modes (*A*, *B* and *C*) were calculated here by eq. (3) where a constant mode Grüneisen parameter ($\gamma_T = \gamma_P$) for each mode was used in the solid phase I of benzene, as stated above. The experimental values of the isothermal mode Grüneisen parameter γ_T were used as the isobaric mode Grüneisen parameter γ_P (Table 3) for all the constant pressures (0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa) in the solid phase I of benzene. Regarding our calculated Raman frequencies for the lattice modes of *A*, *B* and *C* for those constant pressures

(Figs. 1–3), a constant mode Grüneisen parameter (γ_P) is adequate to predict the Raman frequency in benzene. It is also reasonable to use a constant γ_P for constant pressures (0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa) to predict the Raman frequencies for the lattice modes of *A*, *B* and *C* since eq. (3) contains the pressure-dependent term $A(P)$. We also note that the coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 of the $A(P)$ term were determined using the values of the volume (Table 2) and the Raman frequencies of the lattice modes (*A*, *B* and *C*) for constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa (Table 4). Thus, using a constant γ_P and the coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 gives an expected behaviour of Raman frequencies for the lattice modes *A*, *B* and *C* according to eq. (3). Our calculated Raman frequencies of those lattice modes can be compared with the experimental data for constant pressures of 0, 1.4 and 3.05 GPa in the solid phase I of benzene, when available in literature.

Conclusions

Raman frequencies of the lattice modes (*A*, *B* and *C*) were calculated as a function of temperature at constant pressures for the solid I of benzene. Volume data was used through the mode Grüneisen parameters for this calculation of the Raman frequencies. It was found that the Raman frequencies of the three lattice modes decrease with increasing temperature, as expected. The pressure dependence of the Raman frequencies of the lattice mode *C* at various temperatures is somehow different from the other lattice modes *B* and *C* in the phase I of benzene. Our calculated Raman frequencies can be compared with the experimental data.

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